

Effectiveness of Three Different Retreatment Techniques In Single Canals Filled With Warm Vertical Compaction Technique: An In Vitro Study

Aarya Agarwal¹
V.K. Shetty²
Sonal Bansal³
Amit Eppar⁴
Divyanshi Sharma⁵

PG Student¹
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

Professor & Head²
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

Professor³
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

PG Student⁴
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

PG Student⁵
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

Quick Response Code

Submitted 09 May 2026
Accepted 16 May 2026
Published 12 June 2026

Access this Article Online

Website: www.healtalk.in

DOI

Abstract

Background: Complete removal of gutta-percha during endodontic retreatment remains a clinical challenge, particularly in canals obturated using warm vertical compaction.

Aim: To compare the effectiveness of H-files, Coltene Hyflex Remover, and ultrasonic endodontic tips in the removal of gutta-percha from root canals.

Materials and Methods: Fifty-four extracted single-rooted mandibular premolars were prepared and obturated using the warm vertical compaction technique. The samples were randomly divided into three groups (n = 18): Group I (H-files), Group II (Hyflex Remover), and Group III (Ultrasonic tips). Retreatment was performed using respective techniques. Residual filling material was evaluated in coronal, middle, and apical thirds using a stereomicroscope at 20× magnification and quantified using ImageJ software. Data were analysed using one-way ANOVA and Student's t-test (p < 0.05).

Results: Significant differences were observed among all groups in each canal third (p < 0.05). Group II demonstrated the lowest residual filling material in coronal (17.05 ± 2.37), middle (22.55 ± 1.85), and apical thirds (29.64 ± 1.38), followed by Group III and Group I. No significant difference was observed between Groups II and III in the coronal third, while Group II showed superior performance in the middle and apical thirds. The apical third exhibited the highest residual material across all groups.

Conclusion: None of the techniques achieved complete removal of obturating material. The Hyflex Remover system demonstrated superior efficacy, followed by ultrasonic tips and H-files, with the apical third remaining the most challenging region for retreatment.

Keywords: Endodontic retreatment, Gutta-percha removal, Hyflex Remover, H-files, Ultrasonic endodontics, Residual filling material.

Introduction

Root canal treatment (RCT) is a highly predictable procedure, with reported success rates of 86%–98%.¹ However, complete healing is not achieved in all cases. Traditionally termed “failure,” such outcomes do not fully reflect the complexity of endodontic prognosis. The concept of *post-treatment disease* has therefore been introduced to better describe the biological status following endodontic therapy.²

Post-treatment disease may result from factors such as missed canals, inadequate cleaning and shaping, coronal leakage, and persistent intra- or extraradicular infection, some of which may only become evident during retreatment. Cross-sectional studies report a high prevalence of apical periodontitis in endodontically treated teeth (30%–65%), with a pooled prevalence of 36%, indicating a substantial need for retreatment.^{3,4}

Endodontic retreatment aims to re-establish canal disinfection by removing existing obturation material and eliminating infection.⁵ Gutta-percha (GP), the most commonly used filling material, can hinder disinfection if not adequately removed.⁶ Various techniques have been proposed for GP removal, including hand instruments, rotary Ni–Ti systems, ultrasonic devices, heat-based methods, and solvents.⁷

Hedström files (H-files) are traditionally used due to their cutting efficiency.⁸ Nickel titanium (Ni–Ti) systems, such as the Coltene Hyflex Remover, offer improved flexibility and cutting efficiency,⁹ while ultrasonic devices enhance debridement through acoustic streaming and cavitation.¹⁰

How to Cite This Article : Agarwal et al. -

Despite these advancements, complete removal of obturation material remains challenging, and comparative evidence among these techniques is limited. Therefore, the present study compares the effectiveness of H-files, Coltene Hyflex Remover Ni-Ti instruments, and ultrasonic endodontic tips in gutta-percha removal during endodontic retreatment.

Materials and Method

This in vitro study was conducted in the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics at Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry and Research Centre. Fifty-four extracted single-rooted mandibular premolars with single canals and fully formed apices were selected. Teeth with calcifications, caries, developmental anomalies, posts, or prior endodontic treatment were excluded. Samples were cleaned and stored in saline until use.

The specimens were decoronated at the cemento-enamel junction and standardized to a canal length of 16 mm. They were randomly divided into three groups (n = 18): Group I (H-files), Group II (Hyflex Remover), and Group III (ultrasonic tips).

Canals were preflared using Gates-Glidden drills (sizes 1–3), and a glide path was established with a size 10 K-file. Instrumentation was performed using stainless steel K-files up to size 50, with apical preparation standardized to size 35. Irrigation was carried out using 5 mL of 5.25% sodium hypochlorite and 5 mL of 17% EDTA. Canals were dried and obturated using the warm vertical compaction technique with gutta-percha and AH Plus sealer. Samples were sealed coronally and stored for two weeks.

During retreatment, irrigation was performed using sodium hypochlorite and EDTA.

- Group I: Retreatment with H-files (sizes 25–50) using circumferential push-pull motion.
- Group II: Hyflex Remover (size 30, 7% taper) operated at 400–800 rpm and 2.5 Ncm torque with a gentle pecking motion up to 2 mm short of working length.
- Group III: Ultrasonic tips (E-3, E-7) used in longitudinal motion, followed by apical finishing with a size 40 K-file.

Final irrigation was performed using sodium hypochlorite and EDTA. Retreatment was considered complete when no visible debris was observed and a size 40 file fit loosely at working length.

Roots were grooved longitudinally and split into two halves. Residual gutta-percha and sealer were evaluated in coronal, middle, and apical thirds using a stereomicroscope at 20× magnification. Images were analyzed using ImageJ software.

Residual filling material (%) was calculated as:

$$\frac{\text{Area of remnant}}{\text{Total canal area}} \times 100$$

Figure 1 - Stereomicroscopic (20×) images showing residual gutta-percha after (A) H-file retreatment, (B) Coltene Hyflex Remover retreatment and (C) Ultrasonic Endodontic tips retreatment.

Complete removal was defined as the absence of visible obturation material both on the instruments and within the canal under stereomicroscopic evaluation.

Data entry and formation of desired results was performed using SPSS version 26.0 (IBM Corporation, Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, N.Y., USA). The data were assessed for normality using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. The data followed the normal distribution; therefore, it was compared by using parametric test. The percentage of residual filling material between groups was compared by using one way ANOVA and it was further analyzed by comparing percentage of residual filling material between two groups by using student t test. The level of statistical significance was set at p < 0.05.

Results

A total of 54 samples (n = 18/group) were evaluated. Data were normally distributed (p > 0.05).

Significant differences were observed among groups in all canal thirds (p < 0.05). In the coronal third, Group II showed the lowest mean residual filling material, followed by Group III and Group I. Similar trends were observed in the middle and apical thirds, with Group II consistently demonstrating the lowest values.

Pairwise comparisons showed that Group II had significantly lower residual filling than Group I in all thirds (p < 0.001), while Group III also showed significantly lower values than Group I (p < 0.05). No significant difference was observed between Groups II and III in the coronal third, whereas Group II demonstrated significantly lower residual filling in the middle and apical thirds.

The apical third exhibited the highest residual filling across all groups.

Mean Percentage of Residual Filling Material

Canal Third	Group I (H-file)	Group II (Hyflex)	Group III (Ultrasonic)	p-value
Coronal	23.29 ± 2.78	17.05 ± 2.37	18.30 ± 2.30	0.001*
Middle	35.46 ± 2.70	22.55 ± 1.85	25.27 ± 1.77	0.001*
Apical	40.38 ± 2.47	29.64 ± 1.38	38.69 ± 2.24	0.001*

Statistically significant (p < 0.05)

Discussion

The present study evaluated and compared the effectiveness of H-files, Coltene Hyflex Remover, and ultrasonic endodontic tips in the removal of gutta-percha from root canals obturated using the warm vertical compaction technique.

Complete removal of obturating material remains a critical step in retreatment, as residual gutta-percha and sealer may harbour microorganisms and limit irrigant penetration, thereby compromising disinfection.⁷ However, none of the tested techniques achieved complete removal, highlighting the inherent difficulty of retreatment procedures.¹¹

Among the techniques evaluated, the Coltene Hyflex Remover system demonstrated the lowest percentage of residual filling material across all canal thirds. This superior performance may be attributed to the properties of nickel titanium instruments, including enhanced flexibility, canal wall adaptation, and cutting efficiency.⁸ Continuous rotary motion further facilitates coronal transportation of softened gutta-percha and promotes more uniform contact with canal walls, improving removal efficiency.^{13, 14}

H-files, representing conventional hand instrumentation, showed the highest amount of residual filling material, particularly in the apical third. This may be attributed to their limited flexibility

and dependence on operator controlled filing motion, which can lead to incomplete engagement of obturating material and apical compaction of debris.^{3,16}

Ultrasonic tips demonstrated intermediate performance. Their mechanism of action, based on acoustic streaming and cavitation, enhances disruption of obturating material and improves irrigant penetration.⁹ However, the absence of continuous mechanical engagement and limited tip penetration in narrow apical regions may reduce their effectiveness, particularly in the apical third.¹ Across all groups, the apical third exhibited the highest residual filling material. This finding can be explained by reduced canal diameter, complex apical anatomy, and deeper penetration of sealer into dentinal tubules, which limit the effectiveness of mechanical instrumentation.^{12,15}

The findings of the present study are consistent with previous studies, which have reported superior efficiency of rotary Ni-Ti retreatment systems compared to hand instrumentation, along with adjunctive benefits of ultrasonic activation.^{17,20} However, the persistence of residual material across all techniques emphasizes that mechanical instrumentation alone is insufficient for complete canal cleanliness.

From a clinical perspective, these results suggest that rotary Ni-Ti retreatment systems may be preferred for bulk removal of obturating material, while ultrasonic techniques may serve as useful adjuncts for enhancing cleaning in canal irregularities.¹⁴

Despite these findings, the study has certain limitations. The in vitro design may not fully replicate clinical conditions, and stereomicroscopic evaluation does not provide three dimensional assessment of residual material.¹² Future studies using advanced imaging techniques such as CBCT or micro-CT may provide more accurate evaluation.^{21,25}

Conclusion

Within the limitations of this in vitro study, none of the evaluated retreatment techniques achieved complete removal of obturating material from root canals obturated using the warm vertical compaction technique. The Coltene Hyflex Remover demonstrated significantly lower residual filling material across all canal thirds compared to H-files and ultrasonic endodontic tips. Ultrasonic tips showed intermediate effectiveness, while H-files exhibited the least efficiency, particularly in the apical third. Across all groups, the apical region remained the most challenging for complete removal.

References

- Pirani C, Pelliccioni GA, Marchionni S, Montebugnoli L, Piana G, Prati C. Effectiveness of three different retreatment techniques in canals filled with compacted gutta-percha or Thermafil: A scanning electron microscope study. *J Endod.* 2009; 35 (10): 1433–1437. Doi: 10.1016/j.joen.2009.06.002.
- Cohen S, Hargreaves KM. Pathways of the Pulp. 11th ed. St. Louis: Mosby Elsevier; 2016. Chapter 8. Page 324.
- Patil A, Mali S, Hegde D, Jaiswal H, Saoji H, Edake DS. Efficacy of rotary and hand instruments in removing gutta-percha and sealer from root canals of endodontically treated teeth. *J Contemp Dent Pract.* 2018;19(8):964–968. doi:10.5005/jp-journals-10024-2366.
- Bhagavaldas MC, Diwan A, Kusumvalli S, Pasha S, Devale M, Chava DC. Efficacy of two rotary retreatment systems in removing gutta-percha and sealer during endodontic retreatment with or without solvent: An in vitro study. *J Conserv Dent.* 2017;20(3):177–181. doi:10.4103/0972-0707.209075.
- Akshay VA, Sirekha A, Reddy J, Champa C, Shetty A, Srinivasan A. Evaluation of the efficacy of TruNatomy, ProTaper retreatment, and RaCe file systems in retreatment of moderately curved mandibular molars: An in vitro study. *J Conserv Dent Endod.* 2023; 26: 383–387
- Zmener O, Pameijer CH, Banegas G. Retreatment efficacy of hand versus automated instrumentation in oval shaped root canals: An ex vivo study. *Int Endod J.* 2006; 39 (7): 521–526. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2591.2006.01100.x.
- Fatima K, Nair R, Khasnis S, Vallabhaneni S, Patil JD. Efficacy of rotary and reciprocating single file systems on different access outlines for gutta-percha removal in retreatment: An in vitro study. *J Conserv Dent.* 2018;21(4):354–358. doi: 10.4103/JCD.JCD_339_17.
- Baigl MM, Kalgeri SH, Kansar N, Patel P, Nair A, Elnawawy MS. Effectiveness of different rotary file systems in removal of gutta-percha during endodontic retreatment with or without solvents: A comparative study. *J Contemp Dent Pract.* 2023; 24 (6): —. doi:10.5005/jp-journals-10024-3523.
- Grande NM, Castagnola R, Minciaccchi I, Marigo L, Plotino G. A review of the latest developments in rotary NiTi technology and root canal preparation. *Aust Dent J.* 2023; 68 (Suppl 1): S24–S38. doi:10.1111/adj.12998.
- Gupta A, Pareek A, Kapila H. Ultrasonics in endodontics: A review. *Int J Health Sci.* 2021; 5 (S1): 264–277. doi:10.53730/ijhs.v5nS1.5602.
- Schirrmeister JF, Meyer KM, Hermanns P, Altenburger MJ, Wrbas KT. Effectiveness of hand and rotary instrumentation for removing a synthetic polymer based root canal obturation material during retreatment. *Int Endod J.* 2006; 39 (2): 150–156.
- Cunha RS, Sigrist De Martin A, Barros PP, da Silva FM, Jacinto RC, da Silveira Bueno CE. In vitro evaluation of the cleansing working time and analysis of the amount of gutta-percha or Resilon remnants on root canal walls after instrumentation for endodontic retreatment. *J Endod.* 2007; 33 (12): 1426–1429. doi:10.1016/j.joen.2007.07.004.
- Gu LS, Ling JQ, Wei X, Huang XY. Efficacy of ProTaper Universal rotary retreatment system for gutta-percha removal from root canals. *Int Endod J.* 2008;41(4):288–295. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2591.2007.01350.x.
- Takahashi CM, Sanches Cunha R, Sigrist De Martin A, Fontana CE, Fernandes MS, da Silveira Bueno CE. In vitro evaluation of the effectiveness of ProTaper Universal rotary retreatment system for gutta-percha removal with or without a solvent. *J Endod.* 2009;35(11):1580–1583. doi:10.1016/j.joen.2009.07.015.
- Ersev H, Yilmaz B, Dinçol ME, Daglaroglu R. The efficacy of ProTaper Universal rotary retreatment instrumentation to remove single gutta-percha cones cemented with several endodontic sealers. *Int Endod J.* 2012; 45 (8): 756–762.
- Chauhan R, Tikku AP, Chandra A. Detection of residual obturation material after root canal retreatment with three different techniques using a dental operating microscope and a stereomicroscope: An in vitro comparative evaluation. *J Conserv Dent.* 2012;15(3):218–222. doi:10.4103/0972-0707.97940.
- Reddy N, Admala SR, Dinapadu S, Pasari S, Reddy PM, Rao MSR. Comparative analysis of efficacy and cleaning ability of hand and rotary devices for gutta-percha removal in root canal retreatment: An in vitro study. *J Contemp Dent Pract.* 2013;14(4):635–643.

18. Tabassum S, Khan FR. Failure of endodontic treatment: The usual suspects. *Eur J Dent.* 2016;10(1):144–147. doi: 10.4103/1305-7456.175682.
19. Tomer AK, Pyasi SK, Dubey S, Sthapak U, Sahani S. Comparison of the efficacy of different file systems to remove filling material during root canal retreatment using stereomicroscope: An in vitro study. *Int J Appl Dent Sci.* 2018; 4 (2): 154–157.
20. Azim AA, Wang HH, Tarrosh M, Azim KA, Piasecki L. Comparison between single file rotary systems: Part 1- Efficiency, effectiveness, and adverse effects in endodontic retreatment. *J Endod.* 2018; 44 (11): 1720–1724. Doi: 10.1016/j.joen.2018.07.022.
21. Rivera-Peña ME, Duarte MAH, Alcalde MP, de Andrade FB, Vivan RR. A novel ultrasonic tip for removal of filling material in flattened/oval-shaped root canals: A micro-CT study. *Braz Oral Res.* 2018;32:e88. doi:10.1590/1807-3107bor-2018.vol32.0088.
22. Agrawal P, Ramanna PK, Arora S, et al. Evaluation of efficacy of different instrumentation for removal of gutta-percha and sealers in endodontic retreatment: An in vitro study. *J Contemp Dent Pract.* 2019; 20 (11):1269–1273.
23. Kaloustian MK, Hachem CE, Zogheib C, Nehme W, Hardan L, Rached P, Kharouf N, Haikel Y, Mancino D. Effectiveness of the REvision system and sonic irrigation in the removal of root canal filling material from oval canals: An in vitro study. *Bio-engineering.* 2020;7(6):260. doi:10.3390/bioengineering9060260.
24. Madhu K, Karade P, Chopade R, Jadhav Y, Chodankar K, Alane U. CBCT evaluation of gutta-percha removal using Pro-Taper and Mtwo retreatment files, WaveOne, and Hedstrom files: An ex vivo study. *Front Dent.* 2021;18:19. doi:10.18502/fid.v18i19.6326.
25. Büyüközer Özkan H, Çimen T, Kaya Apaydın S, Er K. Efficacy of two different retreatment techniques in removing gutta-percha from root canals: A CBCT study. *Turk Endod J.* 2025; 10 (1): 1–9. doi:10.14744/TEJ.2024.13007.